

Farmers considered the damage to be a result of the unexpected drought and took no protective measures.

Infestation started in patches and spread to entire fields. The infested plants became stunted; leaves started to turn yellow and to dry. In severely infested fields, tillers were covered with thousands of nymphs and adults, giving them a whitish, waxy coating. The insect outbreak may be attributed to the inordinate delay of the monsoon rains during the growth phase. The infestation was reduced after the rains. Farmers were advised to spray phosphamidon (0.05%) or dimethoate (0.03%), or to apply carbofuran (0.5 kg a.i./ha) or phorate (1.2 kg a.i./ha) granules.

IRRI 1976 insecticide evaluation results available

The results of laboratory and field evaluation of insecticides conducted at IRRI in 1976 are available. The report includes not only results of coded and named insecticides but also results of various methods of application. The report can be obtained free of charge by writing the Head, Department of Entomology, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Rice insect pests in Laos

G. J. W. Dean, Entomology Department, Rothamsted Experimental Station, Harpenden, Hertfordshire, England

The insect problems of rice in landlocked Laos, where a single crop of predominantly local, glutinous varieties is grown, were investigated in 1973–75. Insect populations were generally low. Insecticide control was usually not required and probably not economically feasible.

The most common pests on upland rice were the Bombay locust *Patanga succincta* L. and the bugs *Nezara viridula* L. and *Leptocoris* spp. In contrast, those insects were uncommon on lowland paddy rice, which had more of the smaller grasshoppers *Oxya* and *Euscirtus* spp. in the seedbeds, and stem borers *Sesamia inferens* (Walk.) and *Chilo* spp. in the transplanted rice. Few rice gall midges *Pachydiplosis oryzae*

(Wood-Mason) or whorl maggots *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino were found.

Few cicadellids and delphacids were found on the local rice varieties; small, experimental plots of IR varieties were often more heavily infested with *Nephotettix* spp. and *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål.

Stem flies in Haringhata, Nadia, West Bengal, India

P. Sen and S. Chakravorty, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kalyani, West Bengal, India

Four stem flies, *Atherigona indica* Mall, *Oscinella* sp., *Steleocerus ensifer* Thom, and *Gaurax* sp., belonging to the families *Anthomyiidae* and *Oscinidae* (Diptera), were found responsible for extensive damage to rice seedlings in upland rice nurseries of four rice varieties.

Damage, starting after the seedlings were about 3 weeks old, was visible even 3 weeks after transplanting. The usual symptoms were the withering of central leaves, yellowing of leaf sheaths, and root rot.

Mortality among young seedlings in field nurseries may even reach 50% in a transplanted experimental plot it was 33%.

Infestation rates in the different varieties of the aus and aman rices tested were significantly different. A maximum of 9.5% infestation was found in the variety Kalma 222 of *aman* rice. In the Dular variety of *aus* rice, the rate was only 0.7%. Different stem fly species were never found on the same plant.

Occurrence of a mite in Tainan District, Taiwan

Yung-Tung Ou, Tainan District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan, Republic of China

Sterility of rice is epidemic in Tainan District during the second crop and causes extensive damage. It has occurred for some time now but its cause is still unknown. Recently, while examining rice ears and sheaths under a microscope, we unexpectedly found many mites. The density of adults and eggs was high.

The mite *Steneotarsonemus madecassus* is new to Taiwan. It could be the major cause of the sterility. Farmers, however, have not been aware of its importance.

Some 2,000 ha have been infested with *S. madecassus* in Tainan District. About 20 percent of the crop was seriously damaged. All varieties except indicas were attacked. The outbreak may be attributed to high levels of synthetic organic phosphorus insecticides applied to rice, and to prohibition of the use of synthetic organic hydrochlorinated insecticides. As one of the phoretic mites, *S. madecassus* may be spread by insects or other arthropods.

Note: Anyone who has observed a similar problem is invited to write to the editor or to Mr. Ou. Replies to IRRN may be published.

A note on the chemical control of *Dichdispa armigera* Olivier in a rice nursery

G. V. Subbaratnam and A. Perraju, Entomology Department, Agricultural College, Bapatla, Guntun District, Andhra Pradesh, India

Because *Diadisa armigera* Olivier has been a serious pest of rice since 1970 in all the coastal districts of Andhra Pradesh, India, the effect of various chemicals (granular and spray) against hispa in the nursery was studied. Tested in granular form were chlorpyrifos, basudin, carbaryl-lindane, disulfoton, phorate, monocrotophos, endosulfan, BHC, fenthion, chlorfenvinphos, and quinalphos. Tested in sprays were fenitrothion, dichlorvos, phosphamidon, Ambithion, carbofuran, and monocrotophos. The granular formulation was applied with the seed. The germination rates of seed, the phytotoxic effects of the chemicals, and the mortality of the beetles released on the germinated seedlings were recorded. Length of root and shoot, number of leaves, and wet and dry weights were measured. The foliar chemicals were sprayed 15 days after sowing. Beetles were released on the seedlings 15 days after sowing; their mortality was recorded daily up to 35 days after sowing.

None of the insecticides retarded seedling growth at the tested doses. Chlorpyrifos, disulfoton, monocrotophos, endosulfan, and basudin favored seedling growth. Of the granular formulations, phorate at 12.5, 10.0, and 7.5 kg a.i./kg seed per hectare was effective against the pest both in initial and residual toxicities; it was closely followed by chlorfenvinphos and disulfoton at 12.5

kg a.i. Next in order of effectiveness were chlorfenvinphos and disulfoton at 10.0 kg a.i., fenthion at 12.5 and 10.0 kg a.i., and quinalphos and chlorpyrifos at 12.5 kg a.i. Among the foliar sprays, carbofuran at concentrations of 0.1% and 0.075% was superior. Monocrotophos was next in effectiveness.

It was concluded that a single application of phorate at 7.5 kg a.i./350

kg seed per hectare, applied along with rice seed, can keep it free of the adult *D. armigera* throughout the nursery period. Carbofuran at 0.1% is the choice among foliar sprays. The granules were tried at high levels to check for adverse effect on the seedlings. Very low levels of 1 to 1.5 kg ai. were also found effective.

Residues of phorate-gamma BHC and mephosfolan in Jaya grain and straw

P. B. Chatterjee, entomologist, Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Pandua, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

Granular insecticides, introduced on a large scale in India during 1967 and 1968 have become popular with Indian farmers. Following application, translocation may result in retention of small quantities of poisons or their metabolites in the plant tissue. In view of the possible health hazard, it is imperative to analyze quantitatively the residue to find out if it is below or above the tolerance limit.

Two recently introduced granular insecticides, phorate-gamma BHC — Paddigard 7.5 G, containing 5% phorate (thimet) plus 2.5% BHC — and

mephosfolan (Cytrolane 5 G), were tested during boro (summer season) to determine the residues in the grain and straw of Jaya.

Table 2. Cytrolane residue^a in Jaya rice grain and straw.

Treatment	Cytrolane (ppm)	
	Grain	Straw
Cytrolane 5 G 0.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.03	0.13
Cytrolane 5 G 0.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.06	0.36
Cytrolane 5 G 1.0 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.06	0.13
Cytrolane 5 G 1.0 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.04	0.28
Control	0.04	0.01

^aMean of 3 replicates.
DT = days after transplanting.

Table 1. Phorate and gamma BHC residues^a in Jaya rice grain and straw, Burdwan, India.

Treatment	Phorate (ppm)	Phorate oxygen analogue sulphone (ppm)	Phorate oxygen analogue (ppm)	Phorate sulphone (ppm)	Gamma BHC (ppm)
<i>Grain</i>					
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT ^b	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
Control (grain)	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
<i>Straw</i>					
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.06
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.06
Control (straw)	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.06

^aMean of 3 replicates. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

Each of the seven treatments was replicated three times in the experimental plots in Burdwan, India. Impounded water was maintained at a depth of about 4 cm during the vegetative and reproductive phases. The soil was fine loamy (clay loam). After harvest, random samples of rice and straw were airshipped to the ACCO Product Development Laboratory, Europe-African Region, Gosport, England, for gas-liquid chromatographic assay. The results are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests

P. B. Chatterjee, entomologist, Department of Agriculture, Pandua, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

The intensification of farming practices, deforestation, indiscriminate use of pesticides (especially broad-spectrum and persistent ones) and a consequent decline in population of natural enemies of insects, and other disrupting forces in the ecosystem have accentuated the problem of insect pests on rice, particularly in the warm and humid tropics. Generally the nontolerant high-yielding rice varieties (HYV) suffer most from insect damage, especially during kharif (wet season) when the main rice crop is grown. Low yield associated with the kharif crop may be one reason for limited use of HW during that season.

An "Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests," drawn up by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, started to function during kharif 1975 in the pest-prone area of Pandua, Bengal. Its principal objectives are 1) to determine why only about 15